

INNOVATIONS OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING IN THE TECHNOLOGIES OF GROWING AGRICULTURAL CROPS

*N. Trykina, lecturer;
D. Trykin, the chief engineer is a designer;
Dm. Trykin, student
Central Ukrainian National Technical University*

Modern agricultural engineering does not just create agricultural machines and equipment - it offers high-tech solutions that allow to increase the efficiency, accuracy, uniformity and economy of the sowing process. This is especially true for precision sowing technologies, when applying which it is important to maintain uniformity of embedding depth and proper contact of the seed with the soil, control the row elements, adapt the machines to the field conditions and reduce losses due to uneven germination or ungerminated seeds.

All equipment manufacturers pay attention to these issues, as producers use all possible means available to obtain high crop yields. Among such manufacturers is the company "Precision Planting", which offers a series of such sowing solutions that complement or modernize existing seed drills.

The Precision Planting brand is a leading provider of precision farming technology and equipment. The company specializes in developing intelligent solutions that help farmers improve the efficiency of their growing processes to achieve higher crop yields. [1-13].

Precision Planting's main activities are aimed at:

- modernization of existing equipment: the company offers solutions that can be installed on seed drills and other equipment from various manufacturers (both domestic and European brands, including John Deere, Maschio Gaspardo, Monosem) to turn it into a high-precision system;
- improvement of precision seeding technology: develops innovative systems, such as ESet vacuum sets and Delta Force downforce control systems, which ensure sowing accuracy of up to 99%, regardless of driving speed (up to 16 km/h) and field conditions;
- develops fertilizer application solutions: offers systems for precise application of liquid fertilizers, which optimizes resource use and reduces costs;
- conducts continuous monitoring and analytics: provides monitors and software for collecting data during sowing, which allows farmers to make informed decisions and improve farm management.

An example of innovative developments for high-quality sowing is PrecisionPlanting CleanSweep - a row cleaner control system, which consists of pneumatic cylinders that allow you to change the pressure/pressure of the cleaner without leaving the cabin [14].

Another development by PrecisionPlanting, DeltaForce, is an automatic system for controlling the downforce on each row of the planter, which replaces springs or pneumatic beams with hydraulic cylinders with weight sensors [15].

The PrecisionPlanting FurrowForce automated furrow closing system is a two-stage mechanism that adapts to seeding conditions, removing air pockets, compacting the soil and conserving moisture.

The PrecisionPlanting Keeton Seed Firmer gently presses each seed into the bottom of the furrow, improving seed-to-soil contact [16].

The next development is the PrecisionPlanting mSet multi-hybrid planting system - it allows you to sow two hybrid seeds from one hopper, switching "on the fly" depending on the field area.

The PrecisionPlanting Ready Row Unit seeding unit kit allows you to update or modernize existing planters by replacing only the row sections, not the entire unit [5].

PrecisionPlanting SmartDepth seeding depth adjustment system allows you to quickly change the depth of each row section from the cab depending on field conditions [4].

All these solutions from the company "Precision Planting" are not just "additional options", but elements that eliminate real problems in the sowing process: different depths, uneven contact of seeds with the soil, uncrushed predecessor residues, variations in the field in the plane, insufficient control, and so on.

Investing in such systems by farmers is advisable, because when the farm already has significant sown areas, this requires a more thorough approach to the accuracy of all technological measures. To do this, farmers are recommended to assess the condition of their fields, taking into account the existing crop residues, soil heterogeneity, problems with depth or compaction; calculate the farm's losses due to insufficient accuracy and the use of a ready-made solution.

At the same time, it is worth considering that modernization requires compatibility with the equipment available on the farm, operator training, and service support.

References

1. PRECISION PLANTING. Official site. URL: <https://www.precisionplanting.com/> (date of application 1.10.2025).
2. Precision Maxx. mSet – Multi-Hybrid Planting System; Ready Row Unit; Reveal Row Cleaner. URL: <https://www.precisionmaxx.com/products/precision-planting/> (date of application 11.10.2025).
3. <https://traktorist.ua/brands/precision-planting> (date of application 5.10.2025).
4. https://arkgroupp.com.ua/ua/g132796244-precision-planting?srsId=AfmBOorsR39krIQ3NJh3jCYGhQ9dip84g_7IzdS5mu2FUQRvocZu7AQ2 (date of application 5.10.2025).
5. <https://www.smartfarming.ua/ohlyad-tekhnohohiy-precision-planting/> (date of application 5.10.2025).
6. https://agsolutions.chcnv.com/?gad_source=1&gad_campaignid=22852286143&gclid=Cj0KCQiA9OnJBhD-ARIsAPV51xP0n0ZZZ7sYhrMVnObj1Gbk-bgvmwB4DPI9iw9IFPLs2B4Yf1JdeJAaArZnEALw_wcB (date of application 5.10.2025).
7. https://www.singularxyz.com/product_detail/SAgro200?gad_source=1&gad_campaignid=19785144452&gclid=Cj0KCQiA9OnJBhD-ARIsAPV51xNjLyMc2tRacTFMN1s1tGbVA5nyyGTUsCs45z_Ric8HocnS67dMt3kaAoxUEALw_wcB (date of application 5.10.2025).
8. Vasytkovska, K. Researches of pneumatic sowing machine with peripheral cells location and inertial superfluous seeds extraction [Text] / K. Vasytkovska, O. Vasytkovskyy, O. Anisimov, N. Trykina // ECONTechMOD. AN INTERNATIONAL QUARTERLY JOURNAL –Lublin; Rzeszow. Vol. 4. No. 4. 2015, 85-89.
9. Васильковська, К. В. Точний висів просапних культур крок до програмування врожаю / К. В. Васильковська, Н. М. Трикіна, О. М. Васильковський // Вісник Українського відділення Міжнародної академії аграрної освіти. - Вип. 4. Херсон: ОЛДІ-ПЛЮС. 2016. - С. 88-97.
10. Vasytkovska K. Characterization of peripherally based cells of the pneumatic-mechanical seeding machine of accurate sowing for tilled crops / K. Vasytkovska, O. Vasytkovskyy, S. Leschenko, D. Petrenko // Конструювання, виробництво та експлуатація сільськогосподарських машин. Загальнодержавний міжвідомчий науково-технічний збірник. Вип. 44 – Кіровоград: КНТУ, 2014. – С. 3-6.
11. Abramova, V., Vasytkovskyy O., Vasytkovska K. Defining quality work of a pneumatic seeding device with an extra disk. ECONTechMOD: an international quarterly journal on economics of technology and modelling processes. – Lublin; Rzeszow. Vol. 5. No. 3. 2016, 191-196.
12. Vasytkovska K.V., Leshchenko S.M., Vasytkovskyy O.M., Petrenko D.I. (2016) Improvement of equipment for basic tillage and sowing as initial stage of harvest forecasting. *INMATEH - Agricultural Engineering*, 50(3). 13-20. (DOI: <https://inmateh.eu/volumes/old-volume/volume-50-no-3-2016/article/improvement-of-equipment-for-basic-tillage-and-sowing-as-initial-stage-of-harvest-forecasting>)
13. Vasytkovska K.V., Vasytkovskyy O.M., Sviren M.O., Kulik G.A. (2018) Analysis of the works performed by pneumatic and mechanical seeding device without using vacuum. *INMATEH - Agricultural Engineering*, 56(3). 25-30.
14. Tonner Precision Services. DeltaForce – Automatic Downforce Control System. URL: <https://www.tonnerprecision.com/products/precision-planting/deltaforce> (date of application 3.10.2025).
15. Precision Planting. SmartDepth – Depth Control System. URL: <https://www.precisionplanting.com/products/planters/smartdepth> (date of application 5.10.2025).
16. Precision Agri Services Inc. Precision Planting Products Overview. URL: <https://www.precisionagriservices.com> (date of application 10.10.2025).